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Multi-modal imaging for porosity quantification in partially-impregnated UD woven glass fibre/ polypropylene composites

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Table of Contents

- Industrial Context and Objectives
 - Process
 - Scientific Problem
- Experimental Work
- Imaging Techniques
 - Fluorescence Microscopy (FM)
 - Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)
 - Micro-computed Tomography (μ -CT)
- Micro-structure Analyses – Multi-modal Imaging
- Conclusions and Perspective

1. Classification of composite manufacturing processes

2. Process-induced defects

3. Compression flow forming: Case of thermoplastic (TP) matrix

4. Residual porosity: a potential defect

Porosity can refer to one of the following flaws:

- Unfilled reinforcement regions;
- Trapped air bubbles (void) ;
- Cavities caused by the shrinkage of TP matrix

(Zuhudi et al., 2021)
(Mehdikhani et al., 2019)

Compression Flow Modeling Process

SEM micrograph: Porosity (trapped air bubbles/void)

■ **Inter-bundle**

■ **Inter-fibre**

Mechanical deformation (Structural mechanics)

(TexGen -MICRA)

→ Decrease in permeability 'K'

→ Mesoscale (preform permeability)

→ Microscale (Bundle permeability)

Melt TP matrix (Fluid mechanics)

Darcy's Law: (1D transverse flow)

$$\vec{v} = - \left(\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla P \right)$$

(Binetruy *et al.*, 2015)

Objective: To identify a correlation between formation of **residual porosity** with the **compaction ratio** as a processing control parameter?

Type	Imaging Tech.	Structural Analysis & Scale							
		Macro (plate)		Meso (yarn)			Micro (single fiber)		
		Fiber Bed	Porosity	Yarns	Porosity	Degree of Imp.	Single fiber	Porosity	Degree of Imp.
2D (+ polishing)	OM	[7] CF/epoxy prepreg	[7, 8] CF prepreg; GF/epoxy (Size & Shape, A_f)	[9] CF/epoxy (Shape)	[10] GF/epoxy (V_f)	[11] Woven CF/PA6	[12] UD CF/PEEK prepreg (Avg. diameter)	[13] CGSC/SiNC (V_f)	[11] Woven CF/PA6
	SEM	[14] CF/epoxy prepreg	[15] CMCs (V_f)	[16] 3DAW-CF/Al	[17] CF/PA66 (A_f)	[18] AF/PLA	[19] SiCf/SiC (Avg. diameter)	[20] Plain Weave CF /PA66 (V_f)	[20] CF Plain Weave/PA66
	FM		[8] GF/epoxy (Size & Shape, A_f)						
3D NDT	μ -CT	[21] Cross-ply GF/epoxy	[7, 22] CF/epoxy; PEEK prepreg (V_f ; 3D localization)	[23] Woven CF/epoxy	[23] Woven CF/epoxy (V_f)	[18] AF/PLA		[13, 24] CGSC/SiNC; SiCf/SiC (V_f)	[25] Knitted GF/PP

[*] : Ref. reporting the use of multiple imaging techniques

- There is no explicit protocol for combining multi modal imaging for TP matrix composites
- In this study, priority is given to combining FM and SEM (μ -CT technique as a perspective)

(Little et al. 2012); (Abdelal and Donaldson 2017); (Khaled et al. 2021); (Gagani et al. 2018); (Ishida et al. 2020); (Oromiehie et al. 2019); (Santhosh et al. 2018); (Breister et al. 2020); (Purslow 1984); (WANG et al. 2021); (Ekoi et al. 2021); (Zou et al. 2022); (Tatlisu et al. 2011); (Liu et al. 2015); (Sabuncuoglu et al. 2020); (Amedewovo et al. 2023); (Mehdikhani et al. 2018); (Gao et al. 2022); (Ayadi et al. 2019)

Material

Reinforcement

- UD NCF GF – Chomarat Ruban 8089HM
- Areal weight – 1054 g.m^{-2}
- Density – $2.55 \times 10^6 \text{ g.m}^{-3}$

Thermoplastic Films

- Polypropylene – Total, PPC 13442
- Density – $0.905 \times 10^6 \text{ g.m}^{-3}$
- Melt Flow Index – 100g/ 10 min
- Melting Temperature – $165 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Plate Manufacturing

- No. of plies – 6 GF + 7 PP Films
- Stacking – $[0/90]_3$
- Size – $0.38 \text{ m} \times 0.38 \text{ m}$

- Through thickness flow
- Deformation of fiber bed

Config. 1

- Ref. plate
- Open mould

Config. 2

- Other plates
- Height \neq cst

Compression Flow Forming: Pinette Press

- 120 KN Press
- Disp. precision (0.1 mm)
- Mold : $0.38 \text{ m} \times 0.38 \text{ m}$

Displacement-controlled manufacturing of plates

Optical microscopy observations

Ref. plate (Cr=0%)

Plate 4 (Cr=23%)

Plate 7 (Cr=30%)

Plate 6 (Cr=41%)

↑ Transverse flow direction

1 mm Scale

Calcination tests: ASTM D3171

Macro-scale observations

The change of Cr % can be used to manufacture partially-impregnated plates of different:

- V_f
- Bundle shapes
- Residual thickness of PP layer

Preparation for Microstructure Analyses

Image based analysis for porosity quantification

Microstructure Analyses: Image-based

Example of output images

Macro Scale (Plate thickness)	Meso Scale (Yarn Cross-section)	Micro Scale (Single fiber)

Development of Multi-modal Imaging Technique

Same microstructure / different imaging modes: SEM & Fluorescence Microscopy

Qualitative Analyses of combined FM-SEM images

Advantages and limitations of the suggested FM-SEM based protocol

Macro Scale

- ✓ Layer 1 (0°)
- ✗ Layer 2 (90°)
- ✓ Layer 3 (0°)
- ✗ Layer 4 (90°)
- ✓ Layer 5 (0°)
- ✗ Layer 6 (90°)
- ✓ PP layer

- ★ Inter bundle porosity
- ★ PP impregnated inter bundle channels

Meso Scale

- ▲ Intra bundle porosity
- ▲ PP impregnated single fibers

Micro Scale

- Single GF
- PP
- Porosity

Quantitative Analysis Micro Scale ROI

Extracted ROI

GF 64.17% Void 19.03%

GF 66% Void 17.92%

GF 63.71% Void 2.06%

- From the multi-modal imaging approach, it was demonstrated that the quantitative analyses at the micro scale of mesh deformation, degree of impregnation and porosity percentage can be conducted.
 - From the combined FM-SEM image, we can depict that the variation in degree of impregnation in the mesh as the matrix flow front progressed from layer 6 to layer 1.
 - The Space homogeneity of porosity in mesh belonging to each layer and within the layer is not same. Thus, high standard deviation from the average porosity. This is due to non homogenous flow front of PP matrix when pressure is applied.
 - From the strain plot, it is observed that the layer 5 is more compacted than layer 1 & 3, which results in decreased mesh permeability. However, the porosity levels in layer 5 is low due to proximity to PP matrix in the lay-up.
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- Extending the approach to include μ CT images (on-going work)
 - Extending the approach to correlate image-based quantitative analyses and process control parameters
 - Quantifying uncertainties related to image-based analysis for quantitative porosity analyses

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Qualitative Analyses of Combined FM-SEM images

Advantages and limitations of the suggested SEM-FM based protocol

▪ Ref. plate (Cr=0%)

▪ Plate 7 (Cr=30%)

▪ Plate 6 (Cr=41%)

❑ Advanced Composites Manufacturing: POPCOM Platform

- All Composites materials, including bio-based materials and thermoplastic matrix composites process

❑ Composites Additive Manufacturing, Hybrid Processes

❑ Virtual Engineering, Process, Part and Process Simulation

❑ Non-Destructive Testing, Performance Assessment

❑ Structural Mechanics – Large Scale Fatigue Test Unit

